

The Lviv Action Note

*Priority Directions and Next Practical Steps for
Ukraine–U.S. Cooperation in Science and Education*

Lviv Academic Bridge 2026: Ukraine–U.S. Science & Education Forum
Lviv Polytechnic National University ~ Lviv, Ukraine ~ 11–12 June 2026

1. Preamble

That we gather in Lviv in a year marking both the 250th anniversary of American independence and the 210th anniversary of Lviv Polytechnic is more than a coincidence. It is a reminder that the bonds between our nations are built to last, and that they are built, in no small part, by scholars, scientists, and educators who choose to work together across an ocean.

The participants of Lviv Academic Bridge 2026, meeting at Lviv Polytechnic National University and online from around the world on 11–12 June 2026,

Recalling that this Forum continues in Lviv the dialogue begun during Ukrainian Week in Washington, D.C., in February 2026, where a Ukraine-U.S. science and education forum brought together university leaders, scholars, and public figures from both nations who resolved to move from conversation toward implementation;

Affirming the values that make genuine academic partnership possible: academic freedom, freedom of speech, the open contest of ideas, research integrity and reproducibility, and respect for the cultural, ethical, civic, and spiritual traditions that sustain free scholarly communities;

Recognizing that intellectual capital is a component of national security, and that quality science supports evidence-based decision-making and an effective state;

Acknowledging that Ukraine's reconstruction, already underway, is knowledge-intensive, requiring universities, other research-performing organizations, and research infrastructures to contribute not only through education and knowledge production, but also through research, development, testing, demonstration, and the generation of new technological, educational, social, and humanitarian value;

Mindful that long-standing instruments of cooperation cannot be taken for granted, and that durable partnership must rest less on any single institution or appropriation than on resilient human networks and horizontal ties that outlast political change;

Declaring that the spirit of this Note is to move from requests to proposals, from the posture of an aid recipient to that of an equal co-creator with genuine agency, from solidarity to long-term partnership, from discussion to implementation, and from aid-based models toward joint knowledge creation;

Adopt the following statement of priority directions and next practical steps, offered as a living agenda rather than a binding commitment, and organized around one guiding question: who works with whom, on what, and what comes next.

2. Guiding Principles

1. From requests to proposals. Ukraine enters this partnership not only with urgent needs, but with capabilities, experience, talent, data, and ideas that can create value for both sides. The relationship we seek is reciprocal.

2. The infrastructure of trust. Large, long-cycle investments do not work without shared practices of transparency, reproducibility, and accountability. We treat trust as an operating condition of international cooperation (the working currency of partnership) and hold to a simple principle: don't just believe us, verify us. Verifiability, not assertion, is the foundation we offer.

3. Open as possible, secure as necessary. We embrace open science as a working tool for verification and trust rather than as an end in itself, recognizing, with our partners in the G7 framework, that openness and security are not contradictory but complementary and mutually reinforcing.

4. Friend-shoring in science. We propose reliable, security-aware cooperation chains built among trusted partners. Friend-shoring here does not mean closing academic exchange; it means working with those whose trustworthiness is demonstrated through partnership. This is offered not as a plea but as an invitation to test us, through joint projects, transparent workflows, and accountable delivery.

5. Reverse innovation. Solutions forged under the harder conditions of war (in resilience, continuity under stress, and improvisation) can become relevant to more stable systems. Ukraine's wartime experience is not only a vulnerability to be supported but an asset to be shared.

6. Durability and depoliticization. We favor mechanisms that outlast specific governments: joint institutions, laboratories, grant programs, consortia, and shared publishing platforms, sustained above all by personal connections and human networks.

3. Priority Directions

Direction 1: Equal partnership and joint knowledge creation

- Shift the default unit of cooperation from one-off memoranda to regular, recurring formats of joint expert work: standing working groups, joint calls, paired laboratories, shared research infrastructures, and co-supervised graduate training.
- Pursue co-created research consortia in which Ukrainian institutions are co-applicants and coordinators, not only beneficiaries.
- Give education equal standing with research through co-supervised PhD pathways, joint and double-degree programs, virtual exchange (COIL), summer schools, and mobility fellowships for students and early-career researchers.
- Encourage practical cooperation among Ukrainian and U.S. research funders, including public agencies, national research foundations, philanthropic foundations, and university-based funding mechanisms, through aligned or complementary calls, co-funding windows, expert exchange, and compatible evaluation principles, so that horizontal researcher-to-researcher cooperation is supported by durable grant infrastructure.

Direction 2: The Ukraine–U.S. Open Knowledge Corridor

Open science is treated here not as a symbolic commitment but as a practical mechanism for making Ukrainian research visible, verifiable, interoperable, and fundable to international partners.

- Build a transatlantic community of reviewers and experts in which U.S. academia comes to know, understand, and verify Ukrainian science in working mode.
- Develop shared publishing and peer-review infrastructure and shared open-access platforms; encourage deposit of publications, data, and metadata under open licenses, consistent with the FAIR principles and the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.
- Pursue research-assessment reform along the lines of DORA and the CoARA Agreement, so that Ukrainian research and researchers are evaluated by responsible, qualitative standards that international partners recognize and trust, easing collaboration, peer review, and funding.
- Connect this work with international academic networks that already pool and share scholarly resources on Ukraine, such as the Global Coalition of Ukrainian Studies (GCUS), which unites universities and scholarly communities worldwide to foster and share academically grounded knowledge about Ukraine.
- Establish a coordinating body to sustain this work: this Note calls for a consortium, provisionally Open Knowledge Ukraine (OK-UA, working name to be confirmed), to build, connect, and sustain open scholarly-communication and reproducibility infrastructure for and with Ukraine. It would be open, non-commercial, and community-led, anchored in the Ukrainian Reproducibility Network (UARN), and built incrementally, beginning with this Note as a declaration of intent.
- Align this consortium with established international standards, including the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, the Barcelona Declaration, and the FAIR principles.

Direction 3: Ukraine as a trusted R&D partner (friend-shoring)

- Develop mature data governance, controlled-access procedures, and cybersecurity appropriate to sensitive research, consistent with the G7 common values on research security and integrity.
- Strengthen the conditions that make Ukrainian institutions eligible and reliable administrators of U.S. federal research funds, including alignment of financial-administrative procedures with the U.S. Uniform Guidance (2 CFR Part 200).
- Strengthen research-integrity practice and a culture of research security: conflict-of-interest and disclosure norms, transparent authorship and data practices, clear misconduct procedures, and staff training, so that trustworthiness rests on demonstrated practice rather than assertion.

Direction 4: The Ukrainian professional diaspora and brain circulation

- Develop dual-affiliation instruments enabling Ukrainian scholars abroad to hold formal, recognized roles in Ukrainian institutions while remaining where they are.
- Engage the full breadth of the professional diaspora, not only older migration waves but recent forced migrants, and pursue the mental, intellectual, and financial return of expertise even where physical return is not possible.

- Treat the diaspora as a resource rather than a loss, and design mechanisms that counter the “donorship of elites” by ensuring engagement flows benefit Ukrainian institutions directly.
- Build on existing diaspora-engagement initiatives such as the Ukrainian Science Diaspora, a platform supported by the Ministry of Education and Science that connects Ukrainian scholars across migration waves for joint research, mentorship, and reconstruction, working to turn brain drain into brain circulation.

Direction 5: Universities, research institutes, and research infrastructures as engines of postwar reconstruction and reverse innovation

- Position universities, research institutes, and research infrastructures as R&D and testing hubs for reconstruction: knowledge-intensive rebuilding in energy, infrastructure, health, materials, education, and digital systems.
- Document and share Ukraine's wartime reverse innovation: civilian resilience and continuity solutions developed under stress that may benefit partners operating in more stable conditions.
- Develop clear, standardized frameworks for joint intellectual property rights, intellectual asset management, technology transfer, and knowledge valorization, and create academic-industry, academic-public-sector, and academic-civic pathways that move joint R&D from the laboratory toward deployment in reconstruction and wider public benefit.
- Extend the principle of verifiability from research practice to reconstruction itself: where security and privacy allow, use open or controlled-access primary measurement data, including verified measurements of energy generation, infrastructure condition, materials performance, and construction quality, so that rebuilding can be financed, insured, and audited on evidence rather than assertion.
- Pair reconstruction challenges with joint research programs so that rebuilding generates new knowledge rather than only restoring what existed.

Direction 6: People, trust, and resilience

- Invest in the human layer of cooperation: personal networks, mutual visits, long-term relationships, and the horizontal ties that prove resistant to political change.
- Attend to wellbeing, mental health, ethical reflection, and community support as part of system resilience, recognizing that if teams do not endure, procedures do not endure, and the architecture of trust fails.
- Ensure cooperation is reciprocal and non-extractive, with attention to community consent and to the ethics of research conducted with a society under stress.
- Design cooperation to be depoliticized and durable, capable of surviving changes of government on either side.

4. Next Steps

The work begun at the Forum will continue as follow-up: through the two open-access catalogs (both CC BY 4.0) and structured matchmaking between Ukrainian and international partners; through regular online and in-person convenings; and with Lviv Academic Bridge 2026 intended as the first in an ongoing series. A fuller implementation plan, with timelines and partners, will be developed after the Forum, and the Note disseminated to partner ministries, research funders, universities, research institutes, research infrastructures, and networks.

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Acknowledgments and Contact

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